

In memoriam Norman Winfrid Moore (1923–2015)*

Bastiaan Kiauta

Callunastraat 6, 5853 GA Siebengewald / Lb, The Netherlands;
<mbkiauta@gmail.com>

Received and accepted 24th February 2016

Abstract. A short biography of Dr N.W. Moore, the ‘Father of global dragonfly conservation’, is presented with emphasis on and a brief appreciation of his odonatological work.

On 21 October 2015, with the departure of Norman Moore, the Father of global dragonfly conservation (Figs 1, 3, 4), hundreds of odonatologists throughout the World lost a friend and the intimate inspirer and guide in their species and habitat conservation efforts. He had an exceptionally multidimensional scientific profile and his departure is likewise painfully felt in the world of ornithologists, British and other landscape ecologists, managers and conservationists and, not the least, by the workers in the fields of chemical pollution and toxicology in Britain and elsewhere.

Norman W. Moore was born on 24th February 1923 and spent his youth in a large, happy family in East Sussex, initially in Lewes. His grandfather was a president of the Royal College of Physicians and was in 1919 created a baronet. His father, Sir Alan Hilary Moore, was a Medical Officer of Health in Sussex. In his modesty, Norman declined to use the hereditary title “3rd Baronet Hancox”, saying it was not awarded for his personal merits but rather for those of his ancestor.

When Norman was ten, the family moved to Hancox near Battle, in the Weald. In 1936 he went to Eton College and during 1940–1942 he read Natural Sciences at Trinity College in Cambridge, from where he received a 2-year wartime degree before he was called up to the military service. In

* Largely based on an obituary by the same author, published in *Tombo* 58 (2016), Matsumoto, Japan.

1942 he joined the army and during 1943–1947 he served in the Royal Artillery, was sent to the front, was wounded and taken prisoner in Germany. In 1947 he returned to Cambridge, read Part II Zoology and in the Zoology Department he met Janet Singer who, in 1950, became his wife. During 1949–1953 Norman was a Lecturer in the Zoology Department of the University of Bristol. In 1953 he joined the Nature Conservancy as Regional Officer for southeastern England and in 1960 he was appointed Head of its Toxic Chemicals and Wildlife Division. Upon the reorganisation of the Nature Conservancy (1974) he served until his retirement, in 1983, as Chief Advisory Officer of the reconstructed Nature Conservancy Council.

After his retirement, Norman remained in the field of nature conservation as active as ever before, served as Chairman of the National Trust's Wicken Fen Local Management Committee (1985–1996), became founder Chairman of the Odonata Specialist Group of IUCN Species Survival Commission (1980–1999), continued his systematic research on dragonfly com-

Figure 1. Norman Moore on a coast path of the small Channel Island Herm, east of Guernsey (ix-1971). Photo by Janet Moore.

munities and much else. In short: Norman Moore is generally considered as one of the most influential personalities in British nature conservation over half a century. His most important work in this field is the prize-winning semiautobiographical book, *'The bird of time'* (MOORE 1987) – an account on a vital period in British conservation and a call for conservation to be placed higher on the political agenda, since 'conservation is about the future'.

Norman Moore's active involvement in the study of nature commenced in his early childhood by bird watching, as documented by his (unpublished) bird observations, kept since 1929, when he was aged just six, and carried on until the week before his death. True to his saying that 'dragonflies are the bird watcher's insects', he soon expanded his interests to them and his earliest published notes (MOORE 1939, 1942) are related to dragonflies. Influenced by the work of Nikolaas Tinbergen and Konrad Lorenz, he submitted in 1954 his PhD dissertation on the ecology and behaviour of adult Anisoptera at the University of Bristol (MOORE 1954) and published subsequently a series of papers on the territory of dragonflies (and birds) and on dragonfly territorial behaviour. Throughout his life, Norman published well over hundred odonatological publications, mostly related to biology, ecology and behaviour, but including also the annotated Odonata checklist of The Gambia and papers on numerous other subjects, above all, on dragonfly conservation in Britain and worldwide.

I expect Janet has told you about our delightful Norfolk trip earlier this week. On the day she left I had another day's field work visiting Ludham Marshes, where there were lots of A. isosceles, and the Marsham Broad, where I got

Figure 2. Norman Moore's handwriting from a letter to his son Peter (22-vi-2001): »I expect Janet has told you about our delightful Norfolk trip earlier this week. On the day she left I had another day's field work visiting Ludham Marshes, where there were lots of A. isosceles, and the Marsham Broad, where I got... «. Facsimile by courtesy of Dr Peter Moore.

All his manuscripts Norman wrote by hand (Fig. 2) and had them retyped by his secretary or, in later years, by Janet. He never used a typewriter and did not work with the computer either, though he could at all time readily be contacted electronically – through Janet.

MOORE's publications (1991, 2001, 2002) on long-time development of odonate community structure remain the unsurpassed key works in this field.

In 1980 he initiated (for details see MOORE 1982) and chaired (1980–1999) the Odonata Specialist Group (OSG) of the IUCN Species Survival Commission and set up and edited its *Reports*, published by the International Odonatological Society, SIO (parts 1–11; 1982–1996). The OSG work resulted in his book, '*Dragonflies – status survey and conservation action plan*' (MOORE 1997), which is subsequently kept updated and represents the basis for global odonate conservation and protection. As CORBET (1991) empha-

Figure 3. Norman Moore (right) in conversation with Dr Amnuay Pinratana (Brother Philip), Head of the SIO National Office in Thailand, at the Eleventh International Symposium of Odonatology, Trevi, Italy (18–25-viii-1991). Photo by Marianne Kiauta.

sized, in this way Moore provided a needed focus for coordinating odonate conservation projects at the global level and built on an earlier commitment embodied already in the SIO Constitution.

It goes without saying, Norman was Honorary Fellow or Fellow of numerous scientific societies and Member of Honour of SIO. The British Dragonfly Society administers an award in Moore's honour, called the "Norman Moore Award Fund".

At the age of 92 Norman Moore passed away. His wife, Janet, predeceased him in 2014, leaving two daughters, Caroline and Helena, and a son, Peter. His biography and bibliography were published on various occasions. The most authoritative are those compiled by the late Janet and published in his *Festschrift* on the occasion of his 80th birthday (J. MOORE

Figure 4. Norman Moore enjoying the sun in the garden of his home in Swavesey, Cambridgeshire, England (15-iv-2010). Photo by Helena Moore.

2003). The Worldwide Dragonfly Association, WDA, published their volume, 'Guardians of the watershed', as a tribute to Norman Moore's work on the global protection of dragonflies and their habitats (CLAUSNITZER & JÖDICKE 2004). Last but not least, four dragonfly species perpetuate his name in the dragonfly world, viz. *Ceriagrion moorei* Longfield, 1952; *Drepanosticta moorei* Van Tol & Müller, 2003; *Neoneura moorei* Machado, 2003 and *Notogomphus moorei* Vick, 2003. But his greatest monument are all the threatened dragonflies that enjoy protection now – due to Dr Norman Moore's efforts.

References

- CLAUSNITZER V. & JÖDICKE R. (Eds) 2004. Guardians of the watershed. *International Journal of Odonatology* 7: 111-430
- CORBET P.S. 1991. A brief history of odonatology. *Advances in Odonatology* 5: 21-44
- MOORE J. 2003. Norman Winfrid Moore. *Odonatologica* 32: 9-18
- MOORE N.W. 1939. Rare Lepidoptera and Odonata in East Sussex, 1938. *The Entomologist* 1939 (916): 220
- MOORE N.W. 1942. Dragonfly notes. *The Entomologist* 57: 263-264
- MOORE N.W. 1954. On the ecology and behaviour of adult dragonflies (Odonata, Anisoptera). PhD thesis, University of Bristol
- MOORE N.W. 1982. Conservation of Odonata – first steps towards a world strategy. *Advances in Odonatology* 1: 205-211
- MOORE N.W. 1987. The bird of time: the science and politics of nature conservation. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge
- MOORE N.W. 1991. The development of dragonfly communities and the consequences of territorial behaviour: a 27-year study on small ponds at Woodwalton Fen, Cambridgeshire, United Kingdom. *Odonatologica* 22: 203-231
- MOORE N.W. 1997. Dragonflies: status survey and conservation action plan. IUCN, Gland & Cambridge
- MOORE N.W. 2001. Changes in the dragonfly communities at the twenty ponds at Woodwalton Fen, Cambridgeshire, United Kingdom since the study of 1962-1988. *Odonatologica* 30: 289-298
- MOORE N.W. 2002. Oaks, dragonflies and people. Harley Books, Martins, Colchester